

Thermal Decomposition of Irradiated Strontium Nitrate

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The influence of γ -irradiation on the kinetics of thermal decomposition of strontium nitrate has been studied over the temperature range 580-625°. Decomposition occurs in the molten state in four stages, viz., (i) initial gas evolution, (ii) induction, (iii) acceleratory and (iv) decay. The kinetics of stages (i) and (ii) could not be studied with any degree of certainty. The acceleratory and decay stages analyse according to the Prout-Tompkins relationship. Activation energies for these two stages calculated from the Prout-Tompkins constants are 102.9 and 26.3 kcal mole⁻¹, respectively. Irradiation increases initial gas evolution and shortens the induction period. It also enhances the rate constants in the acceleratory and decay stages. The activation energy for the acceleratory stage is diminished while that for the decay stage is increased.

THE role of irradiation in the thermal decomposition of inorganic salts has been studied and it has been observed that preirradiation with energetic radiations shortens the period of induction, if any, and enhances the rate constants for both the acceleratory and the decay stages¹⁻³. Production of chemical damage, displacements and extended lattice defects are the predominant effects of irradiation on systems containing molecular ions⁴⁻⁶. The influences of irradiation on solid decomposition are therefore ascribed to these effects which provide as well as facilitate formation and growth of nucleation centres⁷. In the earlier work^{1,2} the relative contribution of crystal defects and chemical damage fragments was not ascertained. It was therefore of interest to irradiate a substance in the solid state generating both crystal defects and chemical damage and to subsequently follow its decomposition in the molten condition when the crystal defects no longer exist but the chemical damage persists. Strontium nitrate has been chosen for this study because the substance decomposes at temperatures well above the melting point and moreover because the kinetics of thermal annealing of irradiation damage in the substance below its melting point has been studied in detail recently^{8,9}.

Experimental

Material: AR grade strontium nitrate was used in the form of fine powder. It was dried *in vacuo* over phosphorus pentoxide.

Irradiation: Samples sealed in glass ampoules were irradiated with ⁶⁰Co γ -rays to different doses between 100 and 400 Mrad at the dose rate of 0.2 Mrad hr⁻¹. The irradiated samples were also preserved over phosphorus pentoxide before thermal decomposition studies.

Decomposition apparatus and procedure: The decomposition apparatus and procedure employed were the same as those reported earlier¹. Fluorolube HO oil was used as manometric liquid and Kel-F grease as lubricant for stopcocks. In making a run, about 50 mg of strontium nitrate, accurately weighed, was decomposed in a thermostatically controlled electric furnace at temperature in the range 580-625° ($\pm 0.5^\circ$) and the pressure, *p*, of the evolved gases developed at different time intervals was measured at each temperature with a cathetometer. The final pressure *p_f* was obtained by heating at 800° till there was no further pressure rise and then cooling to the respective temperature of each run. The data have all been normalized to a mass of 50 mg. From the pressure values the fractional decomposition $\alpha = p/p_f$ was computed.

Estimation of damage: The nitrite produced by irradiation was estimated spectrophotometrically⁸.

Isothermal annealing: Irradiated crystals were annealed in air isothermally at 300 $\pm 1^\circ$ in a thermostatic electric hot air oven for different time intervals and the extent of annealing determined. The thermal decomposition behaviour of the partially preannealed samples was studied at 600°.

Results and Discussion

Data for the dependence of fractional decomposition, α , for unirradiated strontium nitrate on the heating time, *t*, at different temperatures in the range 580-625° are contained in Fig. 1. The curves are sigmoid in nature, as are characteristic of autocatalytic type reactions, the decomposition proceeding mainly through four stages, viz., (i) initial rapid gas evolution corresponding to $\alpha = 0$, (ii) an

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Fig. 1. Thermal decomposition of unirradiated strontium nitrate at different temperatures.

induction period followed by (iii) acceleratory and (iv) decay stages, respectively.

The initial evolution of gas was extremely rapid and was complete in the first min of heating. It was not possible therefore to determine the kinetics and activation energy of the process. Although the initial reaction in solid decomposition can be ascribed to either physical desorption or to true surface decomposition depending on the activation energy of the process, in decompositions occurring in the molten state, as in the present case, it would only be due to release of occluded air.

The kinetics operating in the induction period also could not be determined with any reasonable degree of certainty. The induction period itself decreases markedly with rise in temperature (Fig. 1).

The α -t curves have been analysed according to the Prout-Tompkins relationship¹⁰ (Fig. 2)

$$\log [\alpha/(1-\alpha)] = k_1 t + c$$

k has two values corresponding to the acceleratory and the decay stages of the reaction. The Arrhenius

Fig. 2. Prout-Tompkins analysis of the kinetics of thermal decomposition of unirradiated strontium nitrate.

plots for the Prout-Tompkins constants k_1 and k_2 are linear and yield activation energies E_1 and E_2 of 102.9 and 26.3 kcal for the acceleratory and the decay stages, respectively (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ACTIVATION ENERGIES FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF STRONTIUM NITRATE (kcal mole⁻¹)

Sample	E_1	E_2
Unirradiated	102.9	26.3
100 Mrad	100.1	30.9
400 Mrad	88.9	39.1

The relation between the measure of the chemical damage⁸ in terms of % NO_2 induced in strontium nitrate in the present experiments and the dose of γ -irradiation is given in Fig. 3. The chemical damage induced is susceptible to thermal recovery. The fraction annealed⁸ at 300° during different time intervals from 0-100 hr in the case of strontium nitrate irradiated to 400 Mrad ⁶⁰Co γ -rays are also shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The dependence of chemical damage in strontium nitrate on the irradiation dose and the time dependence of annealing.

Comparison of the α -t characteristics at 600° for the decomposition of strontium nitrate irradiated to 100, 200, 300 and 400 Mrad ⁶⁰Co γ -rays with those for the unirradiated material (Fig. 4) shows that pronounced changes are brought about in the

Fig. 4. Effect of γ -irradiation dose on the thermal decomposition of strontium nitrate at 600°.

nature of the decomposition by irradiation, particularly at the higher γ -ray doses employed. The induction period is shortened and is virtually absent in the material irradiated to 400 Mrad.

Data for the decomposition of strontium nitrate irradiated to 100 and 400 Mrad over a temperature range 580-625° presented in Figs. 5 and 6 are best fitted by the Prout-Tompkins relationship. The activation energies E_1 and E_2 for the Prout-Tompkins constants are given in Table 1. The results,

Fig. 5. Thermal decomposition of 100 Mrad γ -irradiated strontium nitrate at different temperatures.

Fig. 6. Thermal decomposition of 400 Mrad γ -irradiated strontium nitrate at different temperatures.

which are accurate to $\pm 5\%$, show that whereas the activation energy in the acceleratory stage (E_1) decreases to a small extent on irradiation, that in the decay stage (E_2) increases. That the change upon irradiation is small suggests that the same chemical processes govern the decomposition of both the unirradiated and the irradiated salt. The velocity constants k_1 and k_2 are found to increase with the irradiation dose as seen in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PROUT-TOMPKINS CONSTANTS FOR DIFFERENT γ -IRRADIATION DOSES

Dose, Mrad	Unirrad.	100	200	300	400
k_1 ($\text{min}^{-1} \times 10^3$)	1.143	1.481	1.667	1.905	2.051
k_2 ($\text{min}^{-1} \times 10^3$)	2.50	3.84	4.17	7.69	8.33

It is known that radiation damage, including chemical damage, anneals on gentle heating of the irradiated crystals^{8,9}. But preannealing at 300° for a period upto 100 hr does not change significantly the decomposition characteristics of the irradiated material.

Strontium nitrate melts¹⁴ at 570°, but it is only above 600° that the salt decomposes at a measurable rate^{15,16}. It may therefore be assumed that the entire extent of the reaction takes place in the liquid phase. The overall decomposition of the substance occurs as follows :

The autocatalytic nature of the decomposition is attributable to the product SrO. The catalysing action of the nitrite ion in the decomposition of nitrates may be envisaged as follows. The NO_2 produced during irradiation may act as electron donors and attract oxygen atoms from the neighbouring nitrate ions. The resulting nitrate would then decompose spontaneously.

The Prout-Tompkins¹⁰ analysis for solid decomposition was originally derived on the basis of branching reaction nuclei, i.e., molecules of reactant situated at lattice imperfections mainly on the surface of the solid and possessing a low energy of activation for decomposition^{10,11}. Acceleration of the decomposition occurs when these branching chain nuclei form reactive planes in the material producing mechanical strain which may result in the actual disruption of the crystals. Eventually, these planes interfere with one another and after the time of maximum velocity the reaction rate is controlled by the number of undecomposed molecules present in the system. The situation in the autocatalytic decomposition of strontium nitrate occurring in the melt is similar to the above mechanism and thus the Prout-Tompkins analysis is applicable. In fact, autocatalytic reactions of the Prout-Tompkins type require that all the solid products shall be in a position to catalyse all reactant molecules equally throughout the entire course of the reaction, which is not feasible in a solid because of the low mobility of the reacting constituents but is entirely valid for decompositions occurring in the liquid state as in the present case.

Considerable work has been done on the influence of irradiation on the thermal decomposition of solid substances¹⁷. Generally, the effect of irradiation is to decrease the induction period, if any, and increase the velocity constants for both the acceleratory and decay stages^{1,2}. These effects arise from the chemical damage fragments produced by irradiation constituting decomposition nuclei by themselves or from decomposition nuclei formed as a result of the Wigner energy released on recombination of interstitials and vacancies during the period of initial slow reaction. Subsequently, the centres of decomposed material grow and decomposition spikes create strain sufficient to ultimately fracture the crystal, thus creating new reactive surface where

after the reaction proceeds in an acceleratory manner. No such mechanism can be envisaged for liquid phase decompositions. The NO_2^- formed under irradiation catalyse the decomposition of strontium nitrate occurring in the melt. In consequence the induction period is shortened and the velocity constants of both the acceleratory and the decay stages enhanced as in the influence of irradiation on solid decomposition.

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